

Viscosity Behaviour of the Acid Polysaccharide from *Lannea grandis*

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An acid polysaccharide has been isolated by precipitation with alcohol from an aqueous solution of the plant exudate of *Lannea grandis*. It consists of arabinose, galactose and galacturonic acid. On autohydrolysis arabinose is eliminated forming the degraded acid polysaccharide. The viscosity behaviours of the original and the degraded polyacids, as they obtain with progress of neutralisation, and of the solution of the Na-salt alone and in presence of varying concentrations of NaCl are reported. Using the Flory-Fox equation in an approximate manner the end-to-end separation has been calculated for the polyacids neutralised to different degrees. The polyelectrolyte behaviour is not fully observed in the case of the acids owing perhaps to the stiffness of the polysaccharide chain consisting of 1→6 linked hexose units.

The application of viscosity, light-scattering etc. measurements in order to characterise polyelectrolyte systems is well known¹⁻⁸. The present communication deals with the results of investigation on some of the physico-chemical properties of the acid polysaccharide derived from the exudate of *Lannea grandis*, locally known as "gum Jeol". Mukherjee *et al.*⁹ treated the aqueous solution of the gum as that of hydrophilic colloid. It is now recognised that these systems should preferably be treated as large molecules of colloidal dimensions. From chemical analysis Bhattacharyya *et al.*^{10,10a} suggested the following tentative structures for the repeating units of the original and degraded acid polysaccharides :

Original acid polysaccharide

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On autohydrolysis of an aqueous solution (~15%) of the original polyacid on boiling water bath, the arabinose part was eliminated. The residue was treated in the same manner as the original sample to obtain the degraded polyacid. The ash content of the degraded polysaccharide was 0.29% [α]_D³² $\simeq 2^\circ$ agrees with that reported by Bhattacharyya and Rao¹⁰.

On the basis of the measured equivalent weights, viz., 950 and 1361 respectively for the degraded and original polyacids, the corresponding sodium salts were prepared by adding a slight excess of sodium hydroxide solution. The polysalts were then precipitated with ethanol and centrifuged, triturated several times with absolute ethanol until free from excess alkali, finally washed with ether and dried in vacuum at room temperature.

The polysaccharide solutions once prepared were maintained at 3°-5° to guard against microbial attack, and all necessary measurements with a particular solution were completed within a week or so. During this period the results of measurements were quite reproducible.

Viscosity Measurements: Viscosity measurements were made with a Fenske viscometer having a flow time of 227.5 seconds with water in a water thermostat maintained at (35.0 ± 0.02)°. The solutions being very dilute were assumed to have the same density as water.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

η_{sp}/c vs. c graph for the sodium salts of the degraded and original polyacids are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. In the concentration range studied, η_{sp}/c decreases sharply with increasing concentration instead of rising linearly as in the case of neutral polymers. As the concentration is gradually decreased, counterions diffuse away from the polymer backbone and the repulsion between similarly charged centers on the polymer chain causes the latter to expand. At infinite dilution all the ionizable groups are dissociated and the molecule assumes an extended configuration. The upward rise of the curve

FIG. 1

Plots of η_{sp}/c vs. c of degraded polysalt in water O;
 0.001N NaCl ◻; 0.01N NaCl ◻; 0.1N NaCl ◻; 0.5 N NaCl ●;
 Plots of c/η_{sp} vs. $c^{1/2}$ in water O.

FIG. 2

Plots of η_{sp}/c vs. c of original polysalt in water O;
 0.05N NaCl ◻; 0.5N NaCl ●.
 Plots of c/η_{sp} vs. $c^{1/2}$ in water O.

in the dilute region is thus caused by intramolecular repulsion. In addition, there are the electroviscous effect due to the counterion atmosphere of the macroions and the long range electrostatic coupling between the macromolecules¹¹. Furthermore, not only the size but also the shape of the polymer molecule changes on dilution. Therefore, the upward rise of the η_{sp}/c vs. c curve may be caused by variation of size as well as shape on dilution.

As the concentration is increased, some of the oppositely charged ions are drawn to the polymer chain, thereby neutralising part of the charged centres on the chain. As a result, coiling of the chain becomes increasingly predominant, and in the limit when all the groups are undissociated the coiling is maximum, and the molecule behaves as a flexible charged coil. Reduced viscosity, which is a function of the volume of the dissolved units, therefore decreases with increasing concentration of the polysalts.

The variations of η_{sp}/c with c of the sodium salt of the degraded polyacid in sodium chloride solutions of varying ionic strengths are also shown in Fig. 1. These results are in conformity with the "folding chain" theory of polyelectrolytes. At high concentration of the polysalt in 0.001 N NaCl most of the sodium ions are those from the polysalt itself and hence the η_{sp}/c vs. c curve does not differ appreciably from that of the pure polyelectrolyte in water. But as the polysalt concentration is decreased (the NaCl concentration remaining constant), the upward rise in the η_{sp}/c vs. c curve disappears; instead, the curve becomes concave downwards and goes through a maximum at a point where sodium ion concentration due to the polysalt is about equal to that from NaCl. With stronger NaCl solution (e.g. 0.1 N) the maximum becomes less defined and is shifted towards higher concentration of the polysalt. With still stronger NaCl solution (e.g. 0.5 N) the curve becomes linear as it obtains in the case of a neutral polymer. Similar results have recently been reported for a number of acid polysaccharides¹²⁻¹⁴.

The variation of reduced viscosity with concentration at different degrees of neutralisation (α) of the degraded polyacid is shown in Fig. 3. At comparable concentrations the reduced viscosity increases with increase in the degree of neutralisation. The sodium salt dissociates more and more as neutralisation proceeds, so that the effective charge on the polyion increases. Consequently the molecule expands and the viscosity increases. It is to be noted, however, that in the case of the polyacid and polysalt studied here, the relative rise or fall in the viscosity of the solution is less marked than that of synthetic polyelectrolytes. Such a result is quite expected because, in the case of the polysaccharides, coiling and uncoiling are restricted owing to stereochemical factors. The variation of intrinsic viscosity calculated from the plot of c/η_{sp} vs. $c^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (vide Fig. 1) according to Fuoss's equation,¹⁵ of the degraded polyacid with neutralisation is shown in Table I.

From a knowledge of the intrinsic viscosity, $[\eta]$, and number average molecular weight, \bar{M}_n , it is possible to calculate in an approximate manner the effective root mean

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square separation between the ends of a polymer molecule, $(\overline{R^2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, by means of the well known Flory-Fox¹⁶ equation*:

$$(\overline{R^2})^{3/2} = \frac{\overline{M}_n[\eta]}{\Phi} \quad (3)$$

where Φ is a universal constant, independent of solute-solvent systems, and is equal to 2.1×10^{21} . The number average molecular weight of the degraded and original polysalts, as determined by light scattering measurements¹⁷, using the Brice-Phoenix photometer, have been found to be 8.21×10^5 and 9.80×10^5 respectively. For this purpose, Zimm plots were obtained from carefully measured light-scattering data. Using the values of $[\eta]$ determined from plots of c/η_{sp} vs. $c^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (vide Fig. 4) corresponding to different degrees of neutralisation, α , those of $(\overline{R^2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ have been calculated. The results are shown in Table I

FIG. 3

Plots of η_{sp}/c vs. c of degraded polyacid at different degrees of neutralisation.

FIG. 4

Plots of c/η_{sp} vs. $c^{1/2}$ of degraded polyacid at different degrees of neutralisation.

In order to avoid any possibility of hydrolysis of the polyacids in presence of mineral acids, the effective separation, $(\overline{R^2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, for the completely uncharged polyacid was calculated

TABLE I.

Variation of the average root mean square separation of the degraded polyacid as a function of degree of neutralisation.

Degree of neutralisation α	Intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ (dl/gm)	$(\overline{R^2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (\AA) α
0.00	0.055	278
0.20	0.333	507
0.40	0.400	539
0.60	0.435	554
0.80	0.714	654
1.00	0.476	571

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*The limitation of this equation to highly extended structures as in the present case is recognised. It is, however, to be noted that this equation has been used merely for a comparison of the behaviours of the degraded and original polysalts and that of the degraded polyacid at different degrees of neutralisation.

from the intrinsic viscosity of the corresponding polysalt in 0.5N sodium chloride solution. In this case a linear graph is obtained for $\eta_{sp} c$ vs. c plot from which $[\eta]$ can be evaluated directly (Fig. 1 & Fig. 2) The intrinsic viscosities of the degraded and original polyacids at $\alpha=1$ are taken as those of the corresponding polysalts in water.

From the values of $(\overline{R^2})_{\alpha}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ in Table I, it is clearly observed that the polysaccharide molecule expands with increasing neutralisation and the expansion reaches a maximum value near about 80% neutralisation when the charge density on the polyion is maximum, but afterwards the expansion drops, since with further neutralisation the charge density on the polyion decreases due to increased rate of counterion binding. It is seen from the above table that the value of $(\overline{R^2})_{\alpha}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for the degraded polyacid varies from 278 Å when the molecule is uncharged, to 571 Å when the molecule is fully charged. The $[\eta]$ values for the uncharged and fully charged original polyacids are 0.22 and 2.04 (dl/gm) respectively, the corresponding values of $(\overline{R^2})_{\alpha}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ being 468 Å and 612 Å respectively.

For synthetic polyacids at high degrees of neutralisation, an equilibrium due to the exchange between localized counterions and those free in solution takes place and eventually the amount of counterion binding levels off as α approaches unity¹⁸. However, for polyions which are not sufficiently uncoiled even at high α , some of the counterions may be trapped in the region where $|\epsilon\phi/KT| > 1$, causing a drop in charge density followed by a decrease in chain extension. In the present case since these gum polyacids exhibit only a limited uncoiling with neutralisation caused by stereochemical restrictions of the sugar residues, a drop in $(\overline{R^2})_{\alpha}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ at high α seems to be understandable due to this "volume binding" of the counterions.

The presence of arabinose branching in the original polyacid¹⁰ should cause a reduction in intrinsic viscosity, but the situation here is just the reverse. The result, however, may not appear surprising because of the inherent stiffness and highly polydisperse character of the samples investigated. A better characterisation may be done by carrying out measurements with more homodisperse fractions.

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